

Is COVID-19 a new congenital disease?

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Citation: Jesús Joaquín Hijona Elósegui, Antonio Luis Carballlo García, Ana Cristina Fernández Rísquez, Jesús Carlos presa Lorite, Juan Francisco Expósito Montes María Soledad Sánchez Torices. Is COVID-19 a new congenital disease?. *Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour.*2023;2(17):1-14.

Received Date: 25 October, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 30 October, 2023; **Published Date:** 07 November, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objective: On January 7th, 2020, a new coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, was identified as a new causative agent of human pneumonia. The disease caused by this new pathogen was designated under international consensus as COVID-19. Because of its recent emergence, our current understanding of the impact of this new disease on pregnancy is still limited. One of the questions to unveil is whether vertical transmission occurs during gestation.

Patients and Methods: Real-time PCR (polymerase chain reaction) technique was used to detect the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in vaginal secretions, amniotic fluid, and blood from the umbilical cord in 21 pregnant patients of Caucasian ethnicity exhibiting acute non-severe clinical presentations of COVID-19 during the second and third trimester of pregnancy.

Results: We found no evidence that may suggest a potential transmission of SARS-CoV-2 from the infected mother to the amniotic fluid, cord blood, or vaginal fluid.

Conclusions: Although the sample size under study is limited and only represents non-severe cases of COVID-19, at the present time, there is no evidence of vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy. Considering both, our data and previously communicated observations, it would be reasonable to presume that, in the event that vertical transmission may possibly occur, it would be an uncommon event and hence, congenital defects associated to this disease are not foreseen. Nevertheless, additional time and rigorous observation of COVID-19 cases during pregnancy will contribute to further clarify the real impact that SARS-CoV-2 may have over pregnant women and their newborns, as well as the factors that modulate this disease.

Keywords: Coronavirus; SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19; Congenital disease; Vertical transmission

INTRODUCTION

On December 31st, 2019, the Wuhan Municipal Health Commission in Hubei province (China), reported 27 cases of pneumonia of unknown etiology. The outbreak seemed to have originated at a wholesale market in Wuhan. On January 7th, 2020, a new coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, was identified as the causative agent of this outbreak. The disease caused by this new coronavirus was denominated by international consensus as COVID-19. Near four years after its initial discovery and subsequent acknowledgment as a pandemic, at least 771 million cases have been confirmed worldwide, with an associated mortality surpassing seven million cases (updated information available at <https://covid19.who.int/>).

Due to the multiple observations accrued since its emergence¹, it is estimated that its incubation period can span between 2 and 14 days and that it mainly affects people between 30 and 79 years old, not being necessary a prolonged exposure to the germ to get infected¹. 80% of cases present mild symptoms, but more serious clinical manifestations may occur in up to 20% of those infected¹. The fatality rate ranges between 1 and 6% and, in most of the severe cases, patients have a history of some underlying condition^[1]. Because this is a recent infectious disease, suffering from COVID-19 during pregnancy poses an enigma regarding the maternal-fetal prognosis^[2,3].

It does not appear that pregnant women are more susceptible to suffer COVID-19 nor that, if they present the disease, their respiratory complications are often more serious than in the general population^[2-7]. On the other hand, even growing number of cases documented to date of COVID-19 during the peripartum, no solid evidence has been found suggesting maternal-fetal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy^[2-6]. Likewise, no vertical intrauterine transmission has been described for other coronaviruses similar to SARS-CoV-2, such as SARS-CoV (responsible for Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome) or MERS-CoV (causing Middle East Respiratory Syndrome)^[7]. Neonatal COVID-19 cases have been described, some of them with severe adverse effects on affected newborns, however, none of these cases can unequivocally be associated with the transmission of the virus during pregnancy^[2].

With this study, based on the strict observation of a series of 21 cases of COVID-19 during pregnancy, we intend to provide objective information to this matter.

HYPOTHESIS AND OBJECTIVES

It is unknown whether maternal-fetal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 occurs during pregnancy. Although cases of neonatal infection have been described in children of mothers affected by COVID-19 during the peripartum period, so far it has not been possible to clarify whether these infections result from viral transmission during pregnancy, or if they are the consequence of an infection acquired by the newborn immediately after birth, by mechanisms analogous to those that caused the infection in its mother.

Trying to achieve a SARS-CoV-2-free neonatal environment is not feasible. Therefore, the only reliable way to evaluate the possible vertical transmission of the germ during pregnancy is to investigate its presence inside the uterus before the birth. At the present time, it is considered that the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in amniotic fluid and/or umbilical cord blood at a time prior to birth, when the amniotic bag is still intact and provided that the sampling has been performed in the maximum possible aseptic conditions, it is the best possible evidence of intrauterine maternal-fetal transmission of coronavirus^[8-12]. The identification of the virus in the placenta cannot be considered as a reliable indicator of intrauterine vertical transmission, given the filter effect that trophoblastic tissue can exert^[13,14].

The challenge of evaluating the possible intrauterine vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2, as previously mentioned, resides in that obtaining samples of amniotic fluid and umbilical cord blood requires the performance of invasive techniques (called amniocentesis and cordocentesis, respectively), which are not exempt from maternal and fetal risks, and which cannot be merely justified for research purposes only. These procedures are frequently performed in daily clinical practice, although always in the context of the diagnosis and treatment of various pathologies, among which maternal COVID-19 is not included.

The objective of this study is to explore the possible intrauterine vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in patients affected by COVID-19 during pregnancy. To achieve this, we proposed to use viral identification techniques in samples of amniotic fluid and venous cord blood extracted from patients subjected to invasive techniques for screening and prenatal treatment of various fetal pathologies, when these were performed during an acute maternal infection by coronavirus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Using real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction techniques for SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acids, the possible presence of the germ was examined in vaginal discharge, venous cord blood and amniotic fluid from 21 Caucasian pregnant patients displaying acute COVID-19 presentations. The viral targets for detection were the genes RdRP, S and E.

All cases corresponded to pregnant women in their second or third trimester of gestation who underwent amniocentesis or cordocentesis for reasons other than COVID-19 and who were suffering an active SARS-CoV-2 infection confirmed at the time of the invasive technique.

This study did not include those cases in which the course of maternal COVID-19 discouraged the performance of the invasive technique, mainly due to maternal clinical instability, as well as those observations derived from pregnant women in which a premature rupture of the lesions could not be ruled out, given the risk of bias associated with possible contamination of the samples derived from the rise of SARS-CoV-2 through the birth canal.

In all cases under study, the puncture performed to obtain the samples was carried out transabdominally with ultrasound guidance and following the usual aseptic techniques included in the “Clinical Practice Guide for Prenatal Diagnosis of Congenital Defects and Chromosomal Abnormalities Screening” of the Spanish Society of Gynecology and Obstetrics (available at www.prosego.es). The equipment used for sample collection was closed-circuit and sterile, and the puncture needle was in all cases uncovered immediately prior to the skin puncture, minimizing the chances of sample contamination.

RESULTS

Out of the 21 cases evaluated, 17 corresponded to pregnant women subjected to amniocentesis for prenatal diagnosis purposes, whereas the remaining 4 cases underwent cordocentesis. The cases of amniocentesis intended to rule out a chromosomal abnormality originated from pregnant women in whom there was a late uptake for the control of pregnancy, because when the suspicion of aneuploidy arises before week ^[15], a chorionic biopsy is prescribed rather than amniocentesis.

Table 1 summarizes the main clinical and analytical variables of the cases studied. As can be seen, there is no evidence to suggest a possible SARS-CoV-2 transmission from the infected mother to either amniotic fluid or cord blood.

Table 1: Main clinical and analytical variables analyzed in the 21 cases included in the series

	Maternal and gestational age	Reason for performing the invasive technique	Maternal status at the moment of invasive technique	Maternal status 14 days after the invasive technique	Result of RT-PCR (SARS-CoV-2) in vaginal discharge	Result of RT-PCR (SARS-CoV-2) in amniotic fluid/ cord blood
CASE 1	31 years - 16 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M - Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 2	39 years - 16 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M - Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 3	27 years - 21 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 4	40 years - 24 weeks	Suspicion of Cytomegalovirus infection	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 5	38 years - 20 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M - Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
	17 years - 16 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative

CASE 6						
CASE 7	39 years - 29 weeks	Rh isoimmunization	PCR + Ig M - Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 8	37 years - 21 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 9	36 years - 21 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 10	33 years - 20 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 11	27 years - 17 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 12	41 years - 27 weeks	Suspicion of Cytomegalovirus infection	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative

CASE 13	17 years - 29 weeks	Suspicion of Cytomegalovirus infection	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 14	43 years - 23 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 15	31 years - 16weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 16	21 years - 16weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 17	21 years - 16weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 18	37 years - 29 weeks	Rh isoimmunization	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 19	33 years - 22 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (fetal abnormality)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative

CASE 20	41 years - 15 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR + Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative
CASE 21	16 years - 15 weeks	Suspicion of chromosomopathy (screening test)	PCR + Ig M + Ig G-	PCR - Ig M + Ig G +	Negative	Negative

The maternal clinical course was favorable in all cases, requiring no hospitalization or pharmacological therapy other than the administration of antipyretics and analgesics in 17 cases. Four pregnant women required hospitalization and administration of low-flow oxygen therapy between 2 and 17 days. At the present time, with 3 cases between 2 and 21 weeks after the invasive technique, all pregnancies remain within normality. The rest of the fetuses studied prenatally in this group were born after a normal course of pregnancy and none of which presented diagnostic criteria for COVID-19 in the week after birth, nor positive results for SARS-CoV-2 in the PCR performed on the neonatal nasopharyngeal exudate taken immediately after birth.

Positive PCR results for SARS-CoV-2 in the maternal nasopharyngeal exudate ranged from 15 to 57 days in 16 cases (2 cases are still under follow-up).

DISCUSSION

The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a quick and drastic change in our way of life. It has forced us to face an extremely complex health, economic and social situation, unprecedented in recent history and while it spreaded uncontrollably across all continents, becoming a challenge for the scientific community, day after day it made us question the viability and the effectiveness of traditional health policies, economic and social development models, and the various ways of promoting research, innovation, and scientific knowledge in general.

Its recent emergence in a pandemic scenery has led to an even poorer knowledge about the possible maternal-fetal implications of COVID-19 during pregnancy^[3]. The presence of type 2 angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE-2), considered an essential receptor for the intracytoplasmic entry of SARS-CoV-2, has been described in placental cells ^[13,14].

Currently available data about gestational implications of SARS-CoV-2 infection are discordant. While some author support there is not an increased risk of gestational loss or cesarean delivery in COVID-19 affected pregnant women ^[15], most reviews find an increased risk of gravidic disturbances in COVID-19 affected pregnancies. Better established disturbances are pre-eclampsia and premature birth and rupture of membranes ^[4-6].

Most cases of premature birth associated with the disease have been described as secondary to the need of prematurely ending the pregnancy in the interest of maternal safety ^[5,6]. Cases of delayed intrauterine growth have also been reported. Most severe of them occurred in a pregnant woman affected by a very severe systemic condition, which makes it difficult to determine whether the gestational complication was secondary to infection or to maternal deterioration itself ^[16-18].

A recent systematic review on the prognosis of SARS-CoV-2 infections in newborns suggests that even though it is infrequent, COVID-19 in neonates has a worse prognosis than the same infection in childhood, being neonatal contamination during postpartum the main mechanism to acquire the disease ^[5].

Before SARS-CoV-2, six other species of coronavirus capable of causing infection in humans had been described ^[4]: HCoV-229E, HCoV-NL63, HCoV-OC43, HCoV-HKU1, MERS-CoV y SARS-CoV. The best known in terms of their interaction with pregnancy are SARS and MERS. Both present an important structural analogy with SARS-CoV-2, hence, previous experience accrued with these species could be deemed as a potential predictor of the perinatal behavior of this new coronavirus^[7].

Observational studies carried out with SARS and MERS suggested a strong association between maternal coronavirus infection and the appearance of complications: severe maternal disease, intrauterine growth retardation, premature birth, spontaneous abortion, and higher rate of neonatal admissions to the ICU, as well as maternal and neonatal death. All these perinatal complications seem secondary to postpartum infection since, unlike what occurs with other viruses such as ZIKA and Ebola, the maternal-fetal transmission rate of coronaviruses is presumably very low. In fact, no conclusive cases of vertical transmission have been documented to date ^[2-9,11,12,15-29].

In July 2020 Vivanti and collaborators ^[21] published the surprising “First proven case of transplacental transmission of SARS-CoV-2” in a pregnant woman affected by COVID-19 during the last stage of pregnancy. The authors supported their conclusion in three findings: a higher viral load in the placental tissue compared to that one in the amniotic fluid and maternal blood, the histological evidence of placental inflammation, and the increasing evolution of the viral load in the different neonatal nasopharyngeal smears (viral concentrations at days 3 and 18 of life are greater than at day 1).

Despite the groundbreaking nature of their findings, there are two aspects of Vivanti's communication that remain questionable. Firstly, their article lacks a clear description of the method(s) used by the authors to obtain samples of amniotic fluid and cord blood. Second and most importantly, contrary to the authors' opinion, it does not seem unfeasible an inadvertent contamination of the samples under study, considering that the samples were obtained in a hospital environment with patients hospitalized for COVID-19, that the birth attended by cesarean section required general anesthesia with the subsequent maternal orotracheal intubation, and that the newborn himself was also subjected to orotracheal intubation. It is evident that postpartum neonatal viral isolation, no matter how early it may have been, does not allow to rule out horizontal transmission.

Several authors have described presumed cases of vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy ^[20-26]. Most of them hypothesize that nasopharyngeal isolation of the germ immediately after birth and the presence of IgM in neonatal blood in the first hours of life are surrogate markers of vertical intrauterine transmission of SARS-CoV-2. Both supporting facts are questionable given that viral isolation in the neonate during postpartum, no matter how early it may be, does not allow to rule out horizontal transmission ^[27]. On the other hand, although IgMs do not usually cross the placenta under normal conditions, current tests for their identification have a high rate of false positives ^[26-29].

Furthermore, it cannot be ruled out that COVID-19 may produce a placental pathology capable of increasing its permeability to antibodies. In fact, a rapid decrease in neonatal IgM concentration after birth has been described ^[25], which appears incompatible with the usual kinetics of IgM in congenital infections ^[26-30].

The histological study of placentas from patients affected by COVID-19 in the peripartum has discovered the presence of viral particles across its mass, as well as areas of hypoperfusion and inflammation. The lack of placental co-expression of ACE-2 and TMPRSS2, two receptors involved in the cytoplasmic entry of SARS-CoV-2, may explain its relative insensitivity to transplacental infection. Nevertheless, viral interactions may use different membrane receptors, so that the susceptibility of the tissue to transplacental infection could be broader than is currently believed^[13,14].

The most recent systematic review regarding the possible maternal-fetal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 concludes that to date there is not enough evidence to support it ^[2]. In any event, the conclusions of the existing literature on COVID-19 during pregnancy should be interpreted with caution, for several reasons. In the first place, because the information presented in many of the publications does not allow us to avert duplication; that is, the same observation may appear several times in the literature either as a description of a case or as part of a series, as it was suggested during the SARS epidemic ^[31]. On the other hand, many articles present little or no information on pregnant women and newborns. In this regard, it has been pointed out that the urgency of scientific journals to publish results on COVID-19 has led to weakening the peer review process,

causing articles to be published which, under normal conditions, would have been rejected. Furthermore, it cannot be ruled out that there has been a biased publication of data, recognized as the selection of pregnant women with an excessively favorable or morbid clinical evolution.

Main information about vertical intrauterine transmission of SARS-CoV-2 provide from observational (epidemiological) register. Furthermore, and although it may be obvious, it is convenient not to forget that a negative result in any diagnostic test, even with the most sensitive technique, does not allow to rule out the possibility of infection [2-6]. Obviously, the best evidence of intrauterine transmission of SARS-CoV-2 would be the confirmation of its presence and replication in fetal lung tissue, but this is technically unfeasible. For this reason, viral isolations made from placenta, amniotic fluid and cord blood are considered indirect but reliable indicators of congenital transmission, provided that these samples are taken during pregnancy or immediately after birth and when the sampling has been carried out in strict aseptic conditions to limit the risk of contamination. The only consideration regarding this rule resides in the fact that the identification of SARS-CoV-2 in the placenta cannot be considered as an absolute indicator of vertical intrauterine viral transmission, because of the well-established filter effect that can exert trophoblastic tissue to prevent maternal fetal transfer of certain substances and germs [13-14].

Regarding the laboratory methodology used in our series, it should only be noted that viral detection techniques by means of real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction for SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acids are currently considered the most reliable method for their use in clinic [32].

To date, thousands cases of gestational COVID-19 have been reported in the literature worldwide, most of them occurring in the third trimester and close to birth. The main limitation in many of these descriptions is that they did not always consider all the possible neonatal infection routes: transplacental, ascending through the birth canal or by breastfeeding, apart from the well-known respiratory and contact routes. Indeed, this is precisely where the main significance of our series lies, in which the possible vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 has been evaluated using reliable techniques for viral identification and minimizing the risk of bias associated with possible contamination of the samples.

An important gap in present knowledge is whether the severity of COVID-19 can impact the perinatal transmission rates and the prognosis of infected newborns. The cases collected in our series corresponded to relatively mild cases of the disease, but we should take into account that the study design itself makes it unlikely that, in a situation of severe maternal deterioration, invasive techniques would be performed for the diagnosis and prenatal treatment of certain fetal pathologies, which diagnosis and treatment are unlikely to be a priority in the context of severe maternal COVID-19.

Finally vaccination during pregnancy may represent an element of protection against risks, as well as for the fetus, as 14 of 21 cases analyzed happened in women who had received at least 2 doses of SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. The main contribution of our series is to evaluate the possible vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during the second and third trimesters of pregnancy and outside the birth process, an aspect that remained unknown until now since there is no clinical justification for performing invasive techniques for the prenatal diagnosis of intrauterine coronavirus infection. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first series of these characteristics. The conclusions attained, which remain provisional until additional cases can be studied, are particularly applicable to the intra-amniotic transmission of SARS-CoV-2, since only four cases of cordocentesis were studied. In any case, it is likely that both, cord blood and amniotic fluid, display the phenomenon of maternal-fetal coronavirus transfer with similar reliability since cord blood only infuses a fetus whose urine and secretions from the respiratory tree participate actively in the amount and composition of the amniotic fluid.

CONCLUSIONS

Although the sample studied is limited and represents exclusively mild conditions of COVID-19, at the moment there is no evidence of vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy. From our data and previous communications, it can be presumed that if there is vertical coronavirus transmission, this must be infrequent and therefore it is not foreseeable that congenital defects associated with it may occur. Moreover, it will be time and rigorous observation of COVID-19 cases during pregnancy which will clarify the real influence that SARS-CoV-2 exerts on pregnant women and their offspring, as well as those factors that modulate the disease.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

No potential competing interest was reported by the authors.

REFERENCES

1. Li J, Huang DQ, Zou B, et al. Epidemiology of COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis of clinical characteristics, risk factors, and outcomes. J Med Virol 2021; 93: 1449-1458.
2. Karimi H, Mansouri V, Rezaei N. Vertical transmission and maternal passive immunity post-SARS-CoV-2. Future Virol 2023.
3. Deniz M, Tezer H. Vertical transmission of SARS CoV-2: a systematic review. J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med 2022; 35: 2655-2662.
4. Aljohani MA, Albalawi FM, Albalawi BM et al. Consequences of SARS-CoV-2 Infection in Pregnant Women and Their Infants: A Systematic Review. Cureus 2022; 14: e32787.

5. Simbar M, Nazarpour S, Sheidaei A. Evaluation of pregnancy outcomes in mothers with COVID-19 infection: a systematic review and meta-analysis. J Obstet Gynaecol 2023; 43: 2162867.
6. Ramirez Ubillus GC, Sedano Gelvet EE, et al. Gestational complications associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection in pregnant women during 2020-2021: systematic review of longitudinal studies. J Perinat Med 2022; 51(3): 291-299.
7. Schwartz DA, Graham AL. Potential Maternal and Infant Outcomes from Coronavirus 2019-nCoV (SARS-CoV-2) Infecting Pregnant Women: Lessons from SARS, MERS, and Other Human Coronavirus Infections. Viruses 2020; 12: 194.
8. Favre G, Pomar L, Musso D, et al. 2019-nCoV epidemic: What about pregnancies?. Lancet 2020; 395(10224): e40.
9. Mimouni F, Lakshminrusimha S, Pearlman SA, et al. Perinatal aspects on the COVID-19 pandemic: a practical resource for perinatal–neonatal specialists. Journal of Perinatology 2020; 40: 820-826.
10. Gujski M, Humeniuk E, Bojar I. Current State of Knowledge About SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 Disease in Pregnant Women. Med Sci Monit 2020; 26: e924725.
11. Zeng L, Xia S, Yuan W, et al. Neonatal early-onset infection with SARS-CoV-2 in 33 neonates born to mothers with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China. JAMA Pediatr 2020; 878.
12. Dong L, Tian J, He S, et al. Possible Vertical Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 From an Infected Mother to Her Newborn. JAMA. 2020; 323:1846-1848.
13. Valdes G, Neves L AA, Anton L, et al. Distribution of Angiotensin-(1-7) and ACE2 in Human Placentas of Normal and Pathological Pregnancies. Placenta 2006; 27: 200-207.
14. Pilarska I, Bizon M, Sawicki W. Influence of COVID-19 infection on placental function. Ginekol Pol. 2023; 94(1): 79-83.
15. Cannarella R, Kaiyal RS, Marino M et al. Impact of COVID-19 on Fetal Outcomes in Pregnant Women: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. J Pers Med 2023; 13(9): 1337.
16. Chen H, Guo J, Wang C, et al. Clinical characteristics and intra- uterine vertical transmission potential of COVID-19 infection in nine pregnant women: a retrospective review of medical records. Lancet 2020; 395: 809.
17. Liu Y, Chen H, Tang K, et al. Clinical manifestations and outcome of SARS-CoV-2 infection during pregnancy. J Infect. 2020; S0163-4453(20)30109-2.
18. Wang X, Zhou Z, Zhang J, et al. A case of 2019 Novel Coronavirus in a pregnant woman with preterm delivery. Clin Infect Dis. 2020; 71(15): 844-846.
19. Al-Kuraishy HM, Al-Gareeb AI, Albezrah NKA et al. Pregnancy and COVID-19: high or low risk of vertical transmission. Clin Exp Med. 2023; 23(4): 957-967.
20. Wake AD. Intrauterine Vertical Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 Infection Among Confirmed Cases of Pregnant Women: "A Double Burden for the Pregnant Women"- A Systematic Review. Glob Pediatr Health. 2022; 9: 2333794X221089765.
21. Vivanti AJ, Vauloup-Fellous C, Prevot S, et al. Transplacental transmission of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Nature Communications 2020; 11: 3572.

22. Dong L, Tian J, He S et al. Possible vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 from an infected mother to her newborn. JAMA 2023; 323: 1846-1848.
23. Patane L, Morotti D, Giunta MR et al. Vertical transmission of coronavirus disease 2019: severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 RNA on the fetal side of the placenta in pregnancies with coronavirus disease 2019–positive mothers and neonates at birth. Am J Obstet Gynecol 2023; 2: 3.
24. Ferrazzi E, Frigerio L, Savasi V, et al. Vaginal delivery in SARS-CoV-2 infected pregnant women in Northern Italy: A retrospective analysis. BJOG. 2020; 127: 1116-1121.
25. Wang S, Guo L, Chen W, et al. A case report of neonatal COVID-19 infection in China. Clin Infect Dis. 2020; 71: 853-857.
26. Zeng L, Xia S, Yuan W, et al. Neonatal early-onset infection with SARS-CoV-2 in 33 neonates born to mothers with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China. JAMA Pediatr 2020. 174(7): 722-725.
27. Cabero-Perez MJ, Gómez Acebo I, Dierssen-Sotos T. Infección por SARS-CoV-2 en el embarazo y posibilidad de transmisión al neonato: una revisión sistemática. Semergen. 2020; 46: 47-54.
28. Kotlyar AM, Grechukhina O, Chen A, Popkhadze S, Grimshaw A, Tal O, Taylor HS, Tal R. Vertical transmission of coronavirus disease 2019: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2021; 224(1): 35-53.e3.
29. Thomas P, Alexander PE, Ahmed U et al. Vertical transmission risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection in the third trimester: a systematic scoping review. J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med. 2022; 35: 2387-2394.
30. Kimberlin DW, Stagno S. Can SARS-CoV-2 Infection Be Acquired In Utero? More Definitive Evidence Is Needed. JAMA. 2020; 323: 1788-1789.
31. Schwartz DA, Graham AL. Potential Maternal and Infant Outcomes from (Wuhan) Coronavirus 2019-nCoV Infecting Pregnant Women: Lessons from SARS, MERS, and Other Human Coronavirus Infections. Viruses. 2020; 12(2): 194.
32. Roshan J, D’Cruz A, Currier W, et al. Laboratory Testing Methods for Novel Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2). Front Cell Dev Biol. 2020; 8: 468.